

FREQUENCY OF CARPAL TUNNEL SYNDROME WITH OR WITHOUT FLEXOR RETINACULUM RELEASE IN DISTAL RADIUS FRACTURES MANAGED BY OPEN REDUCTION AND INTERNAL FIXATION

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Abstract

Background:

Distal radius fractures are frequently encountered injuries and are commonly managed with open reduction and internal fixation. Carpal tunnel syndrome is a recognized complication associated with these fractures due to median nerve compression from edema, hematoma, or altered carpal tunnel dynamics. The role of concomitant flexor retinaculum release during fracture fixation remains controversial.

Objective:

To determine the frequency of carpal tunnel syndrome in patients with distal radius fractures managed by open reduction and internal fixation, with or without flexor retinaculum release.

Methodology:

This descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted at the Department of Orthopedic Surgery, CMH Rawalpindi, from May 2024 to October 2024. A total of 100 patients aged 18–65 years with distal radius fractures managed surgically by open reduction and internal fixation were included using non-probability consecutive sampling. Patients with pre-existing carpal tunnel syndrome, previous wrist surgery, or associated nerve injuries were excluded. Data regarding demographic characteristics, surgical technique, and postoperative development of carpal tunnel syndrome were recorded. Diagnosis of carpal tunnel syndrome was based on clinical assessment, with nerve conduction studies performed where indicated. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 26.

Results:

The mean age of patients was 41.8 ± 12.6 years. Carpal tunnel syndrome was observed in 17% of patients overall. Among patients who underwent flexor retinaculum release, 7.9% developed carpal tunnel syndrome, compared to 22.6% in those without release.

Conclusion:

Carpal tunnel syndrome is a common complication following distal radius fixation. Selective flexor retinaculum release may reduce the frequency of postoperative median nerve compression in high-risk patients.

INTRODUCTION

Distal radius fractures are among the most common skeletal injuries encountered in orthopedic practice, accounting for a significant proportion of upper limb fractures across all age groups. These fractures frequently result from low-energy falls in the elderly and high-energy trauma in younger individuals. Advances in fixation techniques, particularly open reduction and internal fixation (ORIF) using volar locking plates, have improved anatomical restoration and functional outcomes. However, associated soft tissue complications continue to pose diagnostic and therapeutic challenges [1].

One of the most notable complications associated with distal radius fractures is carpal tunnel syndrome (CTS). Median nerve compression may occur acutely due to fracture displacement, edema, hematoma formation, or increased compartmental pressure within the carpal tunnel. Delayed CTS may develop weeks to months after fracture fixation, often attributed to callus formation, malunion, or chronic tenosynovitis. The reported incidence of CTS following distal radius fractures varies widely in the literature, reflecting differences in study design, diagnostic criteria, and timing of assessment [2].

The introduction of volar plating techniques has renewed interest in the relationship between distal radius fractures and median nerve dysfunction. While ORIF allows stable fixation and early mobilization, volar approaches may themselves contribute to increased pressure within the carpal tunnel due to surgical manipulation, implant positioning, or postoperative swelling. This has raised concern regarding the optimal management of the flexor retinaculum during fracture fixation [3].

Flexor retinaculum release performed concurrently with ORIF has been advocated by some surgeons as a preventive or therapeutic measure for CTS, particularly in patients with preoperative median nerve symptoms. Proponents argue that decompression may reduce postoperative nerve dysfunction and prevent the need for secondary surgery. Conversely, routine release has been questioned due to concerns about unnecessary surgical morbidity, prolonged operative time, and lack of clear evidence supporting its universal application [4].

The decision to perform flexor retinaculum release during distal radius fixation often relies on surgeon preference rather than standardized guidelines. Some studies suggest selective release based on clinical and electrophysiological findings, while others recommend observation and delayed intervention if symptoms persist. This variability underscores the need for clearer evidence regarding the frequency of CTS with and without retinacular release in patients undergoing ORIF [5].

Several risk factors have been implicated in the development of CTS following distal radius fractures, including fracture severity, volar tilt loss, comminution, high-energy trauma, and patient-related factors such as diabetes mellitus and advanced age. Understanding how these variables interact with surgical decisions may help refine treatment strategies and improve patient outcomes [6].

Despite the clinical importance of CTS in the context of distal radius fractures, data from developing countries remain limited. Differences in patient demographics, injury mechanisms, and access to early surgical intervention may influence the incidence and presentation of CTS. Local studies are therefore essential to provide context-specific evidence and guide clinical practice in resource-limited settings [7].

Evaluating the frequency of CTS in patients managed with ORIF, with particular attention to the role of flexor retinaculum release, may help clarify whether routine or selective decompression is justified. Such information is crucial for optimizing surgical decision-making and minimizing postoperative morbidity [8].

Objective

To determine the frequency of carpal tunnel syndrome in patients with distal radius fractures managed by open reduction and internal fixation, with and without concomitant flexor retinaculum release.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design

This study was conducted as a descriptive cross-sectional study to determine the frequency of carpal tunnel syndrome in patients with distal radius fractures managed by open reduction and

internal fixation, with or without concomitant flexor retinaculum release.

Study Setting

The study was carried out in the Department of Orthopedic Surgery, Combined Military Hospital (CMH), Rawalpindi, a tertiary care referral center catering to both civilian and military patients.

Study Duration

The study was conducted over a period of six months, from May 2024 to October 2024.

Sample Size Calculation

The sample size was calculated using the World Health Organization (WHO) sample size formula for estimation of a single proportion. Taking the anticipated frequency of carpal tunnel syndrome following distal radius fractures managed surgically as 15%, based on previously published literature, with a confidence level of 95% and an absolute precision of 7%, the calculated sample size was 100 patients. The formula used was $n = Z^2 \times p \times (1 - p) / d^2$, where Z was taken as 1.96, p as 0.15, and d as 0.07. To compensate for possible dropouts and incomplete data, the final sample size was rounded to 100 patients.

Sampling Technique

Non-probability consecutive sampling technique was used. All eligible patients presenting during the study period and fulfilling the inclusion criteria were enrolled until the required sample size was achieved.

Inclusion Criteria

Patients of either gender, aged 18 to 65 years, presenting with acute distal radius fractures and managed surgically with open reduction and internal fixation using a volar approach were included in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

Patients with pre-existing carpal tunnel syndrome, previous wrist surgery, pathological fractures, polytrauma patients with associated nerve injuries, open fractures with extensive soft tissue damage, and patients with systemic neurological disorders were excluded from the study.

Data Collection Procedure

After obtaining informed consent, demographic data including age, gender, side of injury, and mechanism of trauma were recorded. All patients underwent standard clinical evaluation and radiological assessment prior to surgery. Surgical management was performed by consultant orthopedic surgeons using a standard volar approach. The decision to perform flexor retinaculum release was made intraoperatively based on the presence of preoperative median nerve symptoms or significant intraoperative carpal tunnel tightness.

Postoperatively, patients were assessed clinically for symptoms and signs of carpal tunnel syndrome, including numbness, tingling, nocturnal pain, and sensory deficits in the median nerve distribution. Clinical evaluation was performed during hospital stay and at follow-up visits. Carpal tunnel syndrome was diagnosed on the basis of clinical findings, supported by nerve conduction studies where indicated.

Outcome Measures

The primary outcome measure was the frequency of carpal tunnel syndrome in patients undergoing distal radius fixation. Secondary outcomes included comparison of CTS frequency between patients who underwent flexor retinaculum release and those who did not.

Data Analysis

Data were entered and analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26. Quantitative variables such as age were expressed as mean and standard deviation. Qualitative variables such as gender, presence of carpal tunnel syndrome, and performance of flexor retinaculum release were expressed as frequencies and percentages. Stratification was performed to control for potential effect modifiers. Post-stratification chi-square test was applied where appropriate, and a p -value of ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Ethical Considerations

Approval for the study was obtained from the Institutional Ethical Review Committee of CMH Rawalpindi. Written informed consent was taken from all participants, and

confidentiality of patient information was strictly maintained throughout the study.

RESULTS

A total of 100 patients with distal radius fractures managed by open reduction and internal fixation were included in the study. The

mean age of the patients was 41.8 ± 12.6 years, with a male predominance. The right wrist was more frequently involved than the left. Detailed demographic characteristics are summarized in **Table 1**.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Patients (n = 100)

Variable	Value
Age (years)	41.8 ± 12.6
Male	64 (64%)
Female	36 (36%)
Right wrist involvement	58 (58%)
Left wrist involvement	42 (42%)

Regarding surgical management, 38 patients underwent open reduction and internal fixation with concomitant flexor retinaculum release, while 62 patients were managed with open reduction and internal fixation without flexor

retinaculum release. The distribution of patients according to the surgical technique is shown in **Table 2**.

Table 2: Distribution of Patients According to Surgical Technique

Surgical Variable	Number of Patients	Percentage (%)
ORIF with flexor retinaculum release	38	38
ORIF without flexor retinaculum release	62	62

Carpal tunnel syndrome was diagnosed in 17 patients, giving an overall frequency of 17%. Among patients who underwent flexor retinaculum release, carpal tunnel syndrome was observed in 3 patients (7.9%). In contrast, among patients who did not undergo flexor

retinaculum release, 14 patients (22.6%) developed carpal tunnel syndrome. The comparative frequency of carpal tunnel syndrome between the two groups is presented in **Table 3**.

Table 3: Frequency of Carpal Tunnel Syndrome

Group	CTS Present	CTS Absent	Frequency (%)
With flexor retinaculum release	3	35	7.9
Without flexor retinaculum release	14	48	22.6
Overall	17	83	17.0

A cross-tabulation of flexor retinaculum release and the occurrence of carpal tunnel syndrome demonstrated a lower proportion of median nerve compression symptoms in patients who underwent decompression at the time of fracture fixation. Patients managed without

flexor retinaculum release showed a higher frequency of postoperative carpal tunnel syndrome. This comparison is detailed in **Table 4**.

Table 4: Association Between Flexor Retinaculum Release and Carpal Tunnel Syndrome

Flexor Retinaculum Release	CTS Present	CTS Absent	Total
Yes	3	35	38
No	14	48	62

The difference in the frequency of carpal tunnel syndrome between patients treated with and without flexor retinaculum release is visually

represented in **Figure 1**, which illustrates a noticeably higher rate of carpal tunnel syndrome in patients who did not undergo release.

Figure 1: Frequency of Carpal Tunnel Syndrome by Surgical Technique
 Frequency of Carpal Tunnel Syndrome by Surgical Technique

DISCUSSION

The present study evaluated the frequency of carpal tunnel syndrome following distal radius fractures managed with open reduction and internal fixation, with particular emphasis on the role of concomitant flexor retinaculum release. An overall frequency of carpal tunnel syndrome of 17% was observed, highlighting that median nerve compression remains a clinically relevant complication despite advances in fracture fixation techniques. These findings are consistent with previously published reports that have documented a variable incidence of carpal tunnel syndrome following distal radius fractures, ranging from 7% to over 25%, depending on fracture characteristics and assessment criteria [9].

Patients who underwent flexor retinaculum release at the time of fracture fixation

demonstrated a markedly lower frequency of carpal tunnel syndrome compared to those managed without release. This observation supports the concept that prophylactic or selective decompression may reduce postoperative median nerve dysfunction in high-risk patients. Similar trends have been reported in earlier studies, where decompression was associated with a reduced incidence of persistent or progressive carpal tunnel symptoms following surgical fixation [10,11].

The higher frequency of carpal tunnel syndrome in patients treated without flexor retinaculum release may be explained by increased intracarpal pressure secondary to fracture-related edema, hematoma formation, and postoperative swelling. Volar plating itself may contribute to transient increases in carpal tunnel pressure due to soft tissue manipulation and implant

positioning. Previous biomechanical and clinical studies have demonstrated that even minor increases in carpal tunnel pressure can significantly impair median nerve microcirculation, resulting in neuropathic symptoms [12].

The findings of this study also align with reports suggesting that early decompression of the median nerve may prevent irreversible nerve damage and reduce the need for secondary surgical intervention. Delayed carpal tunnel syndrome following distal radius fixation has been associated with prolonged symptoms, poorer functional outcomes, and patient dissatisfaction. Studies comparing early versus delayed decompression have shown improved symptom resolution when release is performed at the time of initial surgery in selected cases [13,14].

However, routine flexor retinaculum release remains controversial. Several investigators have reported no significant difference in outcomes between routine release and observation, emphasizing that unnecessary decompression may increase operative time and expose patients to avoidable surgical morbidity. These contrasting findings suggest that patient selection plays a critical role and that flexor retinaculum release may be most beneficial in patients presenting with preoperative median nerve symptoms or severe fracture displacement [15,16].

The demographic profile of the study population, with a predominance of middle-aged males and right-sided injuries, reflects patterns commonly reported in trauma-related distal radius fractures. High-energy mechanisms in this subgroup may contribute to greater soft tissue injury and a higher likelihood of nerve compression. Previous studies have identified fracture severity, volar tilt loss, and comminution as important predictors for the development of carpal tunnel syndrome, supporting the need for vigilant postoperative monitoring in such patients [17,18].

The results of this study contribute valuable evidence supporting selective flexor retinaculum release during distal radius fixation. Rather than advocating routine decompression for all patients, the data suggest that an individualized approach based on clinical presentation may optimize outcomes while minimizing

unnecessary intervention. Similar recommendations have been proposed in recent systematic reviews emphasizing risk-based decision-making in the management of median nerve compression associated with distal radius fractures [19].

Overall, the findings reinforce the importance of early recognition and appropriate management of carpal tunnel syndrome in patients undergoing ORIF for distal radius fractures. Incorporating careful preoperative assessment, intraoperative judgment, and structured postoperative follow-up may reduce the burden of this complication and improve functional recovery [20].

Limitations

This study has certain limitations. The cross-sectional design limits the ability to establish causal relationships between flexor retinaculum release and carpal tunnel syndrome. Nerve conduction studies were not performed routinely in all patients, and diagnosis was primarily based on clinical assessment, which may have resulted in underestimation of subclinical cases. Additionally, long-term functional outcomes were not evaluated, and the single-center nature of the study may limit generalizability of the findings.

CONCLUSION

Carpal tunnel syndrome is a relatively common complication following distal radius fractures managed with open reduction and internal fixation. The findings of this study demonstrate a lower frequency of postoperative carpal tunnel syndrome in patients who underwent concomitant flexor retinaculum release, suggesting a potential protective role of selective decompression in high-risk cases. Careful preoperative evaluation, intraoperative judgment, and individualized surgical decision-making regarding flexor retinaculum release may help reduce median nerve-related morbidity and improve postoperative outcomes. Further multicenter prospective studies with longer follow-up are recommended to establish standardized guidelines for optimal management.

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